

Research Article

Botnet Malware: Behavioural and Algorithmic Analysis for Detection and Prevention

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Abstract: Botnet malware poses a significant threat to network security due to its ability to conduct coordinated cyberattacks while mimicking legitimate traffic patterns. This study presents a dual-layered detection and prevention framework that integrates behavioral profiling with algorithmic analysis to enhance botnet identification. The proposed method combines time-based communication (beaconing) detection with flow threshold analysis to uncover anomalies indicative of command-and-control (C2) activity. Key packet features are extracted from PCAP files using TShark and analyzed via a custom Python script to identify irregular traffic volumes and recurring communication patterns. Suspicious IP addresses are dynamically converted into Suricata rules, enabling real-time alert generation within an intrusion detection system (IDS). An HTML-based reporting module provides a comprehensive visualization of detected activities. The framework was evaluated using CTU-13 datasets and simulated traffic scenarios, demonstrating high detection accuracy with minimal false positives. Results indicate that automated rule generation significantly reduces response time, supporting effective real-time mitigation. This work contributes a modular and lightweight approach suitable for integration into broader network defense architectures.

Keywords: botnet activity; time-based communication; flow threshold; CTU-13.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Botnets are among the most resilient and destructive forms of malware, contributing significantly to the increasing complexity of cyber threats. A botnet consists of a network of compromised devices that attackers can remotely control to execute various malicious activities, including spam distribution, malware propagation, click fraud, credential theft, and Distributed Denial-of-Service (DDoS) attacks (Bhattacharya et al., 2024; Tikekar et al., 2024). The advancement of botnet technologies such as fast-flux DNS (Al-Duwairi et al., 2021), peer-to-peer (P2P) command-and-control (C2) architectures (Boss & Gralla, 2023), domain generation algorithms (DGAs) (Sood & Zeadally, 2016), and encrypted communications (Papadogiannaki & Ioannidis, (2021), has rendered traditional signature-based detection methods increasingly ineffective.

To address these limitations, cybersecurity research has shifted toward behavioral analysis, focusing on dynamic indicators such as timing patterns, traffic anomalies, and recurrent communication behaviors. This study explores botnet behavior and proposes a practical, rule-based detection and prevention framework grounded in algorithmic analysis. Rather than relying on opaque AI-driven approaches, the framework employs interpretable techniques such as traffic flow

thresholding, port scanning detection, and beaconing frequency analysis. These methods are designed to capture behavioral signatures, including high-frequency outbound traffic, repetitive C2 communications, and abnormal port usage. By correlating these features with malicious activity, the study aims to enhance early detection capabilities.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: the Method and Materials section describes the data and technique employed; the Findings section presents the results of the detection framework applied to real and simulated datasets; and finally, the Conclusion summarizes the contributions and outlines potential directions for future research.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study adopts the V-Model methodology (Ponce et al., 2021), as shown in Figure 1, to ensure a systematic and verifiable development process for a lightweight botnet detection framework. The detection strategy focuses on two primary behavioral characteristics of botnets: high outbound traffic flow (Debashi & Vickers, 2018) and periodic C2 communication (Ghafir et al., 2018). To address the first behavior, the Flow Threshold Algorithm was implemented to detect anomalous packet volumes specifically, instances exceeding 1000 packets per minute. Such abnormal outbound flows are strong indicators of spam distribution or DDoS botnet activity. The second behavior was analyzed using Time-Based Communication Analysis, which identifies recurring intervals in packet exchanges. This beaconing pattern is a well-established marker of botnet coordination.

The detection mechanisms were developed using Python and evaluated using the CTU-13 Botnet Dataset, which provides labeled examples of both malicious and benign traffic. This ensured that all testing was conducted on pre-classified data, enhancing the reliability of the evaluation. Packet captures (PCAP files) were processed using TShark, which converted them into CSV format and extracted key fields such as packet size, IP addresses, and timestamps. Following the verification procedures, a custom Python script applied the behavioral detection algorithms to generate Suricata rules, log suspicious IP addresses, and produce HTML-based reports for clear visualization. Suricata was employed as the Intrusion Detection System (IDS) to enforce the generated rules and trigger real-time alerts (Ghazi et al., 2024). All analysis and validation were conducted within a controlled virtual environment specifically configured for dataset processing and traffic simulation. This setup ensured consistency, repeatability, and isolation from external network influences.

Figure 1. V-Model

3. FINDINGS

The evaluation of the proposed rule-based botnet detection framework using the CTU-13 dataset yielded mixed results. While the Time-Based Communication and Flow Threshold algorithms successfully identified malicious activity, their scalability was limited. The system achieved 100% precision, indicating that every flow flagged as malicious was indeed harmful. However, the overall accuracy was only 42.6%, and the recall was notably low at 0.15%, resulting in a weak F1-score of 0.3%. Importantly, the framework produced zero false positives, meaning no benign traffic was misclassified. This suggests that while the system is highly conservative and avoids false alarms, it also fails to detect a significant portion of botnet traffic. The results highlight a critical trade-off between precision and recall, underscoring the need for further refinement to improve detection coverage without compromising reliability. A summary of the performance metrics is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Performance Metrics of Botnet Detector

Metric	Formula	Calculation	Result
Accuracy	$(TP + TN) / (TP + FP + TN + FN)$	$(60 + 30,258) / 71,219$	42.6%
Precision	$TP / (TP + FP)$	$60 / (60 + 0)$	100%
Recall (Detection Rate)	$TP / (TP + FN)$	$60 / (60 + 40,901)$	0.15%
F1-Score	$2 \times (Precision \times Recall) / (...)$	$2 \times (1 \times 0.0015) / (1 + 0.0015)$	0.3%
False Positive Rate	$FP / (FP + TN)$	$0 / (0 + 30,258)$	0%

4. CONCLUSION

This study developed and evaluated a rule-based botnet detection framework that leverages flow threshold analysis and time-based communication profiling to identify malicious network behavior. The system demonstrated strong reliability, achieving 100% precision and a 0% false positive rate, confirming that all flagged traffic was indeed malicious. This level of accuracy makes the framework particularly suitable for environments where operational efficiency and alert fidelity are critical, such as security operations centres (SOCs).

Despite its reliability, the framework exhibited a low recall rate of 0.15%, indicating that the majority of botnet traffic remained undetected. This limitation affects its scalability and effectiveness in large or complex network environments. However, the results affirm that interpretable and lightweight rule-based algorithms can successfully capture key behavioral traits of botnets, offering a solid

foundation for further development. The primary contribution of this study lies in demonstrating that a modular, rule-based approach, grounded in observable traffic patterns can serve as a dependable baseline for botnet detection. It also provides a practical alternative to opaque machine learning models, especially in contexts where explainability and low resource consumption are essential.

Future work should focus on improving recall through several enhancements: refining flow thresholds to detect shorter sessions, applying advanced statistical techniques such as autocorrelation for beaconing analysis, and integrating threat intelligence feeds with Suricata to identify known malicious IPs and domains. Additionally, expanding the evaluation to include diverse datasets beyond CTU-13 and combining rule-based methods with anomaly detection or lightweight machine learning models will improve both accuracy and adaptability. In summary, while the current framework excels in precision and operational reliability, its extension through hybrid techniques is essential for achieving broader and earlier detection of botnet threats in real-world network environments.

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